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COGNITIVE AND MENTAL PROCESSES IN CREATIVE ACTIVITY

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National Institute of Fine Art and Design named after K. Bekhzod

Abstract: the article analyzes the mental and cognitive processes involved in creative activity. In particular, the structural factors of mental, cognitive and creative activity, such as the "forces" and "components" of creativity studied.

Keywords: the forces of creativity, feelings, perception, thinking, imagination, artistic talent.

Artistic creativity carried out through the creative process, which is a set of stages in the work of the artist to translate a certain ideological and figurative design into a finished work of art. The creative process, both in science and in art, is a complex phenomenon, characterized by diverse features. Simultaneously, any creative process has something in common, objectively natural.

For a long time it was believed that it useless to look for something in common in the creative process, that the work of a writer, musician, artist is unique, individual, largely intuitive, uncontrollable and not subject to study. For example, the famous psychologist N. Hartman wrote that there is nothing more inaccessible to study than a creative act. Indeed, the character, form, and method of creative work are constantly evolving and changing.

Yet the ways and methods of creative work can be generalized and classified. The theory of creativity and perception must be considered as a single system that studies the processes and results of scientific and artistic activity. In this case, data from various fields of knowledge are used - philosophy, sociology, aesthetics, literary criticism, art history, psychology and natural sciences.

The disclosure of the main patterns of creative activity in all its branches is also an urgent problem. It generally recognized that the creation of a general theory of creativity should be based on the study of human activity as a special socio-historical phenomenon.

In revealing the essence of artistic creativity, selected such structural factors of creative activity as the "forces of creativity" and "components of creativity". The named factors of artistic creativity (forces and components) are heterogeneous in the epistemological sense: the forces of creativity are the subjective spiritual and practical abilities of the individual, the "mechanisms" of the artistic and creative process, while the components of creativity are the content elements of the artist's spiritual world, the products of reflecting reality and his activity.

The forces of creativity represent the mental life of a person in the form of mental processes (emotional-volitional phenomena, feelings), cognitive processes (sensations, perceptions, thinking, speech, memory, imagination), mental states (psychology of personality - activity, attention) and individual mental personality traits (temperament, character, abilities).

Human mental processes, as a special property of highly organized matter, are an objective phenomenon that constantly develops with humanity from the birth of a person and throughout life and from generation to generation and provides a reflection of objective reality, cognition of it, including in such a form of activity as creativity.

Acting as the basis of creativity, mental processes are presented as some special "mechanisms", "tools" that are based on the material basis of the human body and are closely interconnected with each other and, naturally, with the surrounding objective reality and through which the artistic and creative process is carried out.

Unlike the forces of creativity, which already act to some extent with the birth of a person and in this sense are a kind of fundamental principle of personality development, the components of creativity (knowledge, worldview, artistic method, aesthetic and artistic taste, skill) are acquired in the process of life. They are products of reflection, study, knowledge of reality through the activity of the mental processes of the individual.

Among the variety of creativity forces feelings occupy a special place as reproductive forces, with the help of which a person has a connection with the outside world and reflects it in his mind.

Thinking, as one of the forces of creativity, plays a major role in the analysis, comprehension of the material of reality, reflected through sensations, perceptions, and feelings and imprinted through memory. A deep and comprehensive knowledge of reality is possible only with the participation of thinking, which is the highest cognitive process aimed at revealing the general and essential properties, signs of objects and phenomena and the regular connections between them in order to create a work of art. The functions of thinking in the artist's creative process manifested at all levels of dialectical cognition, from the living contemplation of reality to the auto-editing of the work. The artist's thinking is creative in nature; it works in interaction with creative imagination and in accordance with the peculiarities and specifics of art. The main feature of the artistic thinking is "thinking in images", it is visually figurative.

Imagination as a mental process, along with perception, memory and thinking, plays an important role in human activity. In creativity, imagination acts as one of the main and specific productive and creative forces. In artistic creativity, all types of imagination matter: involuntary and arbitrary, procreative and creative. It allows the artist to create pictures of the past and even the future, often fantastic. Although imagination creates new artistic images, it is based on the knowledge and impressions acquired by the artist in life through sensory perceptions and stored in memory. Therefore, for the active and productive work of the imagination in the creative process, it is necessary to constantly connect the imagination with reality. The deeper the artist knows the world around him, the richer his creative imagination becomes, the more opportunities he has to create truly artistic and authentic images.

Inspiration is a wonderful spiritual state of a person in the process of work. In the creative work of the artist, inspiration plays a significant role and acts as one of the active forces of creativity. From the point of view of psychology, inspiration is defined as a state of colossal tension of all the mental forces, the result of which are significant creative achievements. Inspiration, although it represents a colossal strain of all the creative, spiritual and physical forces of the artist, but in practice creative tasks are solved relatively quickly. This seeming impression of lightness is due to the fact that the artist, having a large supply of life impressions and skill, works creatively and with great enthusiasm. In unison, his creative imagination and figurative thinking are actively working. All this leads to a kind of transition from quantity to quality - to the creation of an artwork as a result of intense inspired work.

Artistic talent is one of the main individual psychological properties of a person and acts as a great active force in artistic creativity. From the point of view of psychology, artistic talent is a particularly favorable combination and interaction of abilities that have

been highly developed in the process of training and education, ensuring the success of artistic creative activity.

Artistic talent is a combination and interaction of all abilities for visual activity. Imagination and thinking ensure the selection of the main, most essential and characteristic in the phenomena of reality, concretization and generalization in the development of an artistic image, the creation of an original composition. Visual memory contributes to the creation of vivid visual images in the mind of the artist and helps to transform them successfully into an artistic image. Developed aesthetic feelings and an emotional attitude to the perceived and depicted object are crucial. Volitional properties of the artist's personality ensure the practical implementation of creative ideas. As well as such auxiliary abilities as the properties of the visual analyzer to reflect the texture of the surface of perceived objects and sensorimotor qualities associated with the actions of the artist's hand, providing a quick and accurate assimilation of new techniques.

Genius is a higher qualitative level of human artistic talent. The concept of genius in artistic creativity defines an exceptionally favorable combination of talents, which allows the artist to create works that are ahead of the art of his contemporary historical era and are of world significance.

References

1. Beghetto, R. A., & Kaufman, J. C. (2009). Intellectual estuaries: Connecting learning and creativity in programs of advanced academics. *Journal of Advanced Academics*, 20, 296-324.
2. Cohen, L. M. (1989). A continuum of adaptive creative behaviors. *Creativity Research Journal*, 2, 169-183.
3. Feist, G. J. (1998). A meta-analysis of personality in scientific and artistic creativity. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 2, 290-309.
4. Runco, M. A. (2004). Creativity. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 55, 657-687.
5. Kaufman, J. C., & Sternberg, R. J. (Eds). (2010). *Cambridge handbook of creativity*. New York: Cambridge University Press.